

Recent records of *Hypolimnas misippus* (Linnaeus, 1764) (Lepidoptera: Nymphalidae) from Madeira, Portugal, with a resumé of historical records from Macaronesia

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Synopsis

Occurrence of the migrant nymphalid butterfly *Hypolimnas misippus* (Linnaeus, 1764), on the islands of Madeira and Porto Santo (Portugal) in November 2012 is reported and discussed. Historical records of *H. misippus* on the islands of Macaronesia (Azores, Canary Islands, Madeira, Cape Verde Islands) are briefly examined; the appearance of the migrant pierid butterfly *Catopsilia florella* Fabricius, 1775, and its apparent failure to persist on Madeira between 1999 and 2003 is also considered. Anecdotal evidence regarding the reason occasional small-scale migrations may fail to persist is briefly explored.

Key words: Macaronesia, Madeira, Porto Santo, Azores, Canary Islands, Cape Verde Islands, butterfly migration, Nymphalidae, Pieridae, *Hypolimnas misippus*, *Catopsilia florella*.

Introduction

The nymphalid butterfly *Hypolimnas misippus* (Linnaeus, 1764), has long been notable for two reasons: firstly as a serial migrant; secondly as what is almost certainly the most celebrated example of butterfly mimicry. The type locality of *H. misippus* is in some doubt. It was described by Linnaeus from 'America', but accepted by most subsequent authors (e.g. Aurivillius, 1882; Corbet, 1941) as probably being from the island of Java in Indonesia. A lectotype ♀ was designated by Honey & Scoble (2001: 350) who included a suggestion from Gerardo Lamas (in litt.) of Surinam (a regular stopping place for ships in the XVII century) or the Virgin Islands as a possible source.

Wherever Linnaeus' material originated, *H. misippus* has a very wide distribution. It occurs throughout sub-Saharan Africa, including many offshore islands, Madagascar, Arabia, Sri Lanka and India, southern Indochina and Malaysia, sporadically through the Indonesian islands to New Guinea, northern

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and eastern Australia, Papua New Guinea including the Bismarck Archipelago, the Solomon Islands, Palau, Yap, Vanuatu and New Caledonia (Parsons, 1998; Braby, 2000; Tennent, 2002; 2005; 2006; 2009; Larsen, 2005). In the Neotropics it has been reported from the Greater and Lesser Antilles, north-east South America, Panama and the Yucatan coast of Mexico. In North America it may have been briefly resident in Florida, recorded in Mississippi and at least once as a 'stray' in North Carolina (Scott, 1986). The species is a renowned migrant, particularly on the edge of its range – at the western Palaearctic 'edge' this includes the Canary Islands and Madeira. In reports of sporadic and small-scale migrations in general, males are encountered much more frequently than females, possibly because males are more mobile.

The male *H. misippus* is a medium-sized, very dark blue, almost black butterfly with a distinctive violet sheen surrounding or incorporating a central white cellular spot on each wing. It varies little throughout its wide range. The female, however, is a remarkably accurate mimic of *Danaus chrysippus* (Linnaeus, 1758) (*D. petilia* (Stoll, 1790), in the Australian region), to a degree where even a specialist might experience some doubt in separating them in flight. Differences are obvious when the butterfly comes to rest, and although *H. misippus* is able to accurately mimic the flight pattern of *D. chrysippus*, it reverts to its nymphaline 'type' when disturbed, with a swift and erratic flight. The female is polymorphic (cf. Larsen, 2005: pl. 61, figs 801c–d), depending on the local *D. chrysippus* phenotype, and includes a form – *alcippoides* Butler, 1883, that corresponds with the white-winged form of *D. chrysippus* f. *alcippoides* Moore, 1883.

Historical occurrence of *H. misippus* on the Macaronesian islands

'Macaronesia' is a phytogeographical region conceived in the late XIX century to incorporate the Azores, Canary Islands and Madeira (including the Selvagens). It later included the Cape Verde Islands and some authors subsequently added continental enclaves in Africa and Portugal (e.g. Sidi Ifni, in the Tiznit region of southern Morocco) (Vanderpoorten, Rumsey & Carine, 2007). Whilst this might be an appropriate floral association of islands, it is less successful so far as butterflies are concerned. Most entomologists are content to restrict 'Macaronesia' to the islands, noting that butterflies of the Azores, Canaries and Madeira are fundamentally Palaearctic in origin, whilst those from the Cape Verde islands have a significant Afrotropical element. It is also noted that, for example, the genus *Laparocerus* Schönherr, 1834 (Coleoptera) includes species restricted to the Canaries, Madeira, Selvagens and Morocco.

Judging from records between 1961 and 1972 from the Cape Verde Islands available to Mendes & Bivar de Sousa (2010), *H. misippus* is fairly common and widespread there. It is said to have been reported from each of the Cape Verde Islands with the exception of Santa Luzia and Sal (Riley, 1893; Aurivillius, 1910; Nyström, 1958; Riley, 1968; Traub & Bauer, 1982; Báez & García, 2005) and, although the cluster of records presented by Mendes & Bivar de Sousa (2010) may represent a period of observation/collecting effort, there seems no reason to doubt that *H. misippus* is resident on the Cape Verde Islands and has been so for a lengthy period of time.

The first formal record of *H. misippus* from the Azores appears to be that of Bernardi (1961: 204), who reported (as a new species record for the islands) a

male specimen of *H. misippus* collected by Dr de Borba Vieiza (probably a typographical error, = Vieira) on São Miguel Island in 1934 and subsequently deposited in the Museum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris. Subsequent authors (Leestmans, 1975; Fernández-Rubio, 1991; Meyer, 1991; 1993; 2003) have sometimes reported the species as 'occasional' on the Azores and Vieira (2006: 36) accepted the species as being encountered 'occasionally' on São Miguel. Vieira & Karsholt (2010: 242) recorded *H. misippus* from São Miguel. It is noted that Leestmans (1975: 91) cites Williams (1930) as also reporting the presence of *H. misippus* on the Azores, which would represent the first record of the species from those islands. In fact, Williams (1930: 232) referred to a reported large migration of birds and butterflies, including *H. misippus*, 200 miles from the Cape Verde Islands in 1866, but did not refer to the Azores.

On the Canary Islands the species was apparently first reported in 1895 (Crompton, 1896) and occasionally thereafter on Tenerife. More recently, Feierabend (1988) collected several males at the end of December 1987 in Vueltas/Valle Gran Rey on La Gomera; Pérez Padrón & Carnero Hernández (1988) recorded both sexes near Tecina/Playa de Santiago in February the following year. This is presumably what prompted Báez (1998) to record *H. misippus* as resident on the Canaries. Subsequently, Mendes & Bivar de Sousa (2010: 10) cited *H. misippus* as 'common on the Canary Islands'; in fact Báez & García (2005: 89) record *H. misippus* from seven of the Cape Verde Islands, but make no mention of the Canaries. Hall & Russell (2000) searched for *H. misippus* on La Gomera in October 1999 without success and, so far as the authors are aware, the butterfly, presumably 'resident' for a short time following migration, did not persist. However, a male *H. misippus* was seen on 22 December 2010 and a female on 1 January 2011 at Playa del Santiago on La Gomera by Klaus Frischkorn (Martin Wiemers, pers. comm.). Photographs taken were reproduced by Tshikolovets (2011: 460). Presumably its occurrence was the result of further small-scale migration.

Records of *H. misippus* from Madeira are few. Cockerell (1923: 244) reported [Malcolm] Burr noting specimens of *Colias hyale* (Linnaeus, 1758) (possibly a migrant from the Iberian Peninsula), '*Danais archippus* (Fabricius, 1793)' (= *Danaus plexippus* (Linnaeus, 1758)) and '*Hypolimnas misippus* ab. *inaria* (Cramer, [1779])' (a female form suggesting an African origin), all presumed to be of Madeiran origin, in the collection of the Seminário at Funchal. Meyer (1993: 140) reported a male apparently labelled 'Quinta Fê, Funchal; 1902' in the Municipal Museum, Funchal, and another male labelled 'Quinta Fé, Funchal, 12.xi.1950'. The occurrence of *H. misippus* on Madeira was regarded by Wakeham-Dawson, Salmon & Aguiar (2001) as 'doubtful'. More recently, Aguiar, Franquinho & Karsholt (2006: 72) noted another male specimen of *H. misippus* collected by Isamberto Silva on Desertas Island, Ilhéu Chão, on 20.xi.1995. The specimen is extant in the private collection of Isamberto Silva and has been examined by Aguiar.

Recent records from Madeira and Porto Santo, autumn 2012

A family visit by one of the authors (David Healey) to the Quinta Splendida Hotel in Caniço, east of Funchal, Madeira, in early November 2012 coincided with a period of atrocious weather. In a break in the weather, on the 4 November,

Photo: David Healey

Fig. 1. *Hypolimnas misippus* ♂ resting on fingers of Ann Healey in grounds of the Quinta Splendida Hotel in Canico, east of Funchal.

Photo: David Healey

Fig. 2. *Hypolimnas misippus* ♂ in grounds of the Quinta Splendida Hotel in Canico east of Funchal.

Photo: André Ferreira

Fig. 3. *Hypolimnas misippus* ♀ in grounds of Porto Santo golf club, feeding on *Lantana camara* (L.).

his wife first noticed an unfamiliar butterfly apparently nectaring at a Poinsettia flower (Euphorbiaceae: *Euphorbia pulcherrima* Willd. ex Klotzsch) in the Winter Garden of the hotel. The butterfly was subsequently identified as a male *Hypolimnas misippus* (Fig. 2). Over the next few days, up to three individual male *H. misippus* were observed in the garden, invariably in the same general area; they were feeding at the flowers of Poinsettia and fallen blossom of *Ceiba speciosa* (A. St.-Hil.) Ravenna (Bombacaceae), known as the Brazilian Kapok Tree or Pink Floss Silk Tree, and chasing other butterflies (male *Hypolimnas* species tend to be strongly territorial). Individuals settled on Ann Healey's outstretched hand (Fig. 1) and a coloured shirt. Other butterfly species present in the garden were *Lampides boeticus* (Linnaeus, 1767), *Leptotes pirithous* (Linnaeus, 1767), *Pieris rapae* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Danaus plexippus* (Linnaeus, 1758) and *Vanessa atalanta* (Linnaeus, 1758).

Another of the authors (André Ferreira) had the opportunity to observe and photograph both sexes of *H. misippus* on Porto Santo – a new record for that island. Two males were photographed on the summit of Pico do Castelo on the 16 November (males are notorious 'hill-toppers'), and a female was photographed (Fig. 3) nectaring at the flowers of *Lantana camara* L. (Verbenaceae) at the Golf Club two days later (18 November).

Finally, Manuel Biscoito, Director of the Science Department at the Funchal City Hall (which includes the Natural History Museum and the Marine Biology Station, both in Funchal), forwarded to Antonio Franquinho Aguiar a YouTube video made of an off-road motor meeting held on Porto Santo on 16.xi.2012 (Freitas, 2012). Two butterflies appear on the video, amid the main feature of

track-racing 4WD vehicles: *V. atalanta* and a slightly chipped male *H. misippus* sitting on a rock with wings open in the sunshine.

The future?

The larvae of *H. misippus* are polyphagous, accepting a wide range of host-plants, as might be expected with such a widespread species. On the Cape Verde Islands larvae were found feeding on *Portulaca oleracea* L. (Portulacaceae) (Mück & Traub, 1987). In Africa, the species utilises various plant genera of the families Acanthaceae, Amaranthaceae, Arecaceae, Convolvulaceae, Malvaceae, Portulacaceae and possibly Moraceae (Ackery, Smith & Vane-Wright, 1995). The butterflies seen by David Healey were in the vicinity of a garden containing indigenous plants from the laurel forest and exotic plants from various parts of the world.

The female of *Hypolimnas misippus* is, as already mentioned, an accurate Müllerian mimic of *Danaus chrysippus*. In many parts of the resident range of the former, the two species occur sympatrically and there is no doubt that *H. misippus* gains a measure of protection from its remarkable similarity to a distasteful model (although there is evidence that some *Hypolimnas* species may also be distasteful to predators). *Danaus chrysippus* does not occur on Madeira. The species was included in the Madeiran fauna by Meyer (1993: 132) on the strength of a specimen without a locality label deposited in the Museu Municipal do Funchal. The specimen is associated with a number, 23907, but there is no data in the museum records associated with that number and the late G. E. Maul of that museum (pers. comm., to António Franquinho Aguiar, pre-1997), considered the specimen unlikely to be of Madeiran origin. Aguiar & Karsholt (2006: 93) accordingly removed *D. chrysippus* from the list of Madeiran Lepidoptera.

One might wonder if a species that depends heavily throughout its range on a strong mimetic relationship with an unpalatable model might be disadvantaged when it reaches a locality where the model is absent. But there are localities where *H. misippus* is known to occur without any obvious mimetic protection. The reason why so many small-scale migrations fail to persist is not known – perhaps parasitoids, or cold spells in an otherwise amenable climate, or lack of sufficiently suitable host-plant, or a combination of these and other factors may be responsible. But it is clear that such events rarely result in resident status and it will be interesting to see whether the migration in autumn 2012 results in establishment of a breeding population and, if so, whether that population persists.

It is noted that the pierid butterfly *Catopsolia florella* (Fabricius, 1775) was first detected on Madeira in the summer of 1999, when many adults were observed flying and ovipositing on *Senna* (= *Cassia*) *didymobotrya* (Fresen.) Irwin & Barneby (Caesalpinaceae). It became relatively common in and around Funchal in the following few years. One of us (Franquinho Aguiar) maintained a database of sightings from which it is clear that the butterfly remained frequent up to and including 2001 (see also Hall & Russell, 2001), but became infrequent in 2002 (one adult seen on 6 January 2002; eight ova on 26 January 2002). The species was seen in July 2003, but appears to have now completely disappeared from Madeira. The reasons for this are not known. A vespid wasp was once observed preying on a *C. florella* larva (Franquinho Aguiar, pers. obs), but the fact that the

only recorded host-plant on Madeira was *S. didymobotrya*, an exotic species that does not exist in the wild on Madeira, may have contributed to its demise. Damage to foliage caused by *C. florella* larvae became so visible that gardeners pruned plants more severely than previously. A shortage of available host-plant may therefore have had a bearing on the lack of persistence of *C. florella* on Madeira.

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Rob Parker correctly identified David Healey's photograph of *H. misippus* at an early stage and, with Eddie John and Torben Larsen, engaged in discussion. Manuel Bischoit, Director of the Funchal City Hall Science Department, kindly brought the YouTube video to the authors' attention.

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